

ISic1483

I.Sicily inscription 1483

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary; dedication

Material

limestone (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.07.23 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gela

Place of origin (modern)

Gela

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Gela, Museo Archeologico

Regionale di Gela

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329977

1. [K]υναίθο ἐμὶ τὸ
2. [ἄγαλ]μα τῷ ἐπόχῳ.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285061

PHI 329977

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1483. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385956>